

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Digital Twin (beta version)

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE D.6 - SUMMER

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Objectives

This document describes the design and on-going development of a web platform for storing and visualizing data describing the Digital Twin of the NODES ecosystem.

The current state of the Digital Twin platform allows to:

- collect data from field measurements and results from digital twin models, either as static datasets or live queries to external data-providing web services;
- visualize data in the form of layers on 3D-terrain maps, with possibly many layers presented at the same time for rich analyses;
- create and authenticate users through login with username and password;
- define the visual style of each dataset, with user-provided custom settings in terms of colors and sizes.

B) Technology and Architecture

The architecture of the system is based on the *microservices* pattern.

The system consists of the following components:

- a *backend server* based on [Spring Boot](#) technology
- a frontend based on [React](#) technology
- a map service powered by [ArcGIS Online](#)

The following figure presents a schema of the technology architecture of the Digital Twin platform.

Backend (server and database)

The backend offers the following features:

- Collect and store geospatial *datasets* locally, stored as files in supported formats.
- Support for LAT-LONG coordinates in WGS84 format to describe points, lines, or shapes.
- Each *dataset* enriches its elements with variable metadata, one of which is to be displayed as the main measurement on the map (e.g. *geodetic jump height, landslide risk level, electricity production value, water consumption value, etc.*).
- Each dataset can be uploaded by the user in the form of a file or queried *live* from an external web service.
- Datasets are grouped into user-defined categories.
- Each dataset can be public or private; only the owner can edit or remove a dataset.

Frontend (*web viewer*)

The frontend leverages the ArcGIS Online geospatial engine in Javascript to display data layers on maps. The frontend is the web interface for:

- uploading new datasets, each associated to a layer on the map
- defining the layer display styles (themes, colors, shapes)
- managing users (back office); users are managed by the system administrator, who can create, modify (e.g. change password) and delete them (only if they have no associated data);
- navigating the geospatial data on 3D maps with terrain elevation and view one or more layers selected from the datasets in the database.

In addition to uploading new data through static files, datasets can be obtained by querying compatible third-party web services. This feature is a work in progress at the moment, and it will provide access to following features.

- Live queries towards external web services, defined by their URL (without authentication) and possibly by the related query parameters.
- Ability to save the live data, obtained from external live services, as a persistent dataset on the database, at the user's request.

Supported Data

The proposed solution must be compatible with the formats supported by the ArcGIS JS geospatial visualization engine. Vector data are supported, but data in different formats are excluded, such as data in raster format, which requires a geo-server capable of providing the tiles. The formats supported at the current stage of development are:

- [GeoJSON](#)
- CSV file

with coordinates in a standard format compatible with ArcGIS JS, e.g. WGS84.

C) Use Case #1 – Collecting static data from files

In this use case, the Digital Twing platform is used to visualize vector data on a map. Vector data can be measurements collected from sensors or results of simulation models, and such data are provided in a static file.

1. The user logs in to the platform;
2. Upload (*upload operation*) of a new *dataset* indicating:
 - a. Dataset name
It must be unique, it will appear in the map layer list.
 - b. Description: free text field
 - c. Files (*GeoJSON or CSV*)
 - d. Category among those available, created by users.
 - e. Style: Each dataset is displayed by a placeholder with a shape and a color, or color scale (visual style).
 - f. The dataset can be public or private.

The platform allows users to download dataset files, in order to be able to analyze them independently.

D) Use case #2 – Querying live data from external services

In this use case, the Digital Twing platform is used to visualize vector data from an external web service, whose URL is publicly accessible on the web, or at least from the platform.

1. The user logs in to the platform;
2. Configure a new *dataset* by indicating:
 - a. Dataset name
It must be unique, it will appear in the *map layer* list.
 - b. Description: free text field
 - c. URL of the service exposing the *live* data
The file format must be one of the supported formats. from ArcGIS Online JS. Example:
<https://developers.arcgis.com/javascript/latest/sample-code/layers-geojson-refresh/>
 - d. Category among those available, created by users.
 - e. Style: Each dataset is displayed by a placeholder with a shape and a color, or color scale (visual style).
 - f. The dataset can be public or private.

Each time the data is uploaded to the map, the remote URL will be queried and the live data will be downloaded and displayed on the map as a *layer*.

E) Use case #3 - Viewing public or restricted data

The data can be published on the platform in public or private mode:

- **Public data:** This can be accessed by anyone browsing the Digital Twin platform. They do not require authentication. Users can download the data file.
- **Restricted data:** This can only be accessed by users who log in to the platform.

An example:

1. The user is **not** logged in to the platform;
2. The platform is loaded with some *predefined* layers;
3. The user can navigate the map and can select one or more *layers* from the available public ones;
4. Select an item of interest (point or area) and view the metadata associated with it in an *in-place pop-up* (key-value list).

F) Release

The platform is currently available in beta version on a test and development server.

We expect to publicly release the Digital Twin platform within 2 months from the writing of the current document.

The actual beta version's code is available with limited access in our repository:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093905>